

Kongsfjorden observatory data sets (last update: 2024-11-05)

One part of the dataset has been published on NIRD (Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data) – Research Data Archive, the other part on the Arctic Data Centre (ADC) by the Norwegian Meteorological Institute. The links below link directly to the datasets. The datasets published in the ADC can also be accessed by the umbrella collection with DOI:

2002-2002a (Apr-Jun limited deployment)

<https://doi.org/10.21343/45DK-A188>

2002-2002b (Jul-Sep limited deployment)

<https://doi.org/10.21343/HXQE-A505>

2003-2003 (May-Sep limited deployment)

<https://doi.org/10.21343/VK6A-PE57>

2003-2004

<https://doi.org/10.21343/1X1Q-X886>

2004-2005

<https://doi.org/10.21343/868E-3Z52>

2005-2006

<https://doi.org/10.21343/XEJV-M809>

2006-2007

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00024>

2007-2008

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00025>

2008-2009

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00026>

2009-2010

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00022>

2010-2011

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00023>

2011-2012

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00020>

2012-2013

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00021>

2013-2014

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00018>

2014-2015

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00019>

2015-2016

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00061>

2016-2017

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00062>

2017-2018

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00065>

2018-2020

NO DATA due to technical issues

2020-2020 (Jan-Sep limited deployment, reduced instrumentation)

<https://doi.org/10.11582/2021.00010>

2020-2021

<https://doi.org/10.21343/6CNG-7S41>

2021-2022

<https://doi.org/10.21343/OSMF-TM10>

2022-2023

<https://doi.org/10.21343/M9EQ-6G51>

2023-2024

<https://doi.org/10.21343/DXC5-VK44>